

AGRICULTURAL LAND USE FACTSHEET

EU MISSION 'A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE'

Healthy soils are essential to life on Earth. They are the foundation of our food systems, they also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience. Yet, between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are considered unhealthy. While it can take hundreds of years to form just one centimetre of soil, it can be lost in a single rainstorm or through industrial damage.

The EC launched the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' - Horizon Europe programme - **to create 100 living labs and lighthouses** in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

Funded by
the European Union

THE MISSION SOIL WILL¹:

- > Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- > Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- > Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- > Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

¹ European Commission

[*more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1

Reduce desertification

2

Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

3

Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils

4

Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

5

Prevent erosion

6

Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

7

Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

8

Improve soil literacy in society

THE MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS ARE...

"user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption." Factsheet - EU Mission Soil Deal for Europe: Living labs and lighthouses."

CHALLENGES IN AGRICULTURAL LAND USE

Agricultural soil challenges (ASC) depend strongly on site-specific conditions in relation to climate, soil type, soil management and socio-economics. ASC are primarily related to Mission objectives 1–6, but the local conditions determine which are most relevant. Achieving the CSA will be possible by acting on objectives 7 and 8 of the Mission Soil and requires the interaction of stakeholders.

Living labs allow tackling complex challenges in a structured approach: Actors, citizens and end-users are involved from the very first moment to co-design innovations and promote rapid upscaling as well as achieving broader and faster social acceptance. Governmental institutions are included to address and overcome regulatory barriers for the uptake of promising new solutions.

Agricultural soil health living labs have to address even broader challenges than the local ones, moving to the regional scale, covering different objectives of the Mission.

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential feature of Living Labs is their **user-centric approach**, involving all key actors and end-users throughout the innovation process. While specific participants vary by context, they can be grouped using the **Quadruple Helix Model**—Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—forming a **Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)** that enables real co-creation and impact.

This inclusive model supports co-learning and ensures that solutions are not only scientifically sound but also practical, economically viable, socially accepted, and environmentally sustainable.

SOME EXAMPLES OF STAKEHOLDERS OF LIVING LABS FOCUSING ON AGRICULTURE INCLUDE:

- **INDUSTRY:** Farmers and landowners, agricultural advisors, contractors, researchers (e.g. from private foundations, companies, innovative labs), agribusiness companies (e.g. agricultural engineers, food engineers, manufacturers of seeds and inorganic fertilisers, retailers) ranging from major European players to innovative startups, investors.
- **CITIZENS:** NGOs (e.g. nature conservation and water protection organisations), citizen groups, and movements (local, regional, and national).
- **ACADEMIA:** Researchers from universities, governmental organisations, research institutes.
- **GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC SECTOR:** Local, regional, and national (e.g. authorities, regulators, researchers).

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THIS FIELD?

Living Labs focusing on agriculture accelerate the development of innovative solutions for soil health by bringing together farmers, researchers, companies, and citizens in a collaborative environment.

These solutions may include climate-smart soil management practices that enhance sustainability and resilience to climate change, as well as adaptations of existing methods to address local challenges.

Moreover, structured collaboration with investors, regulators, and authorities can facilitate faster development, scaling-up of solutions, and the removal of implementation barriers.

WHAT ACTIVITIES CAN A MISSION SOIL LIVING LAB FOCUSING ON AGRICULTURE PERFORM?

Foster collaboration on the co-design of new solutions by:

- Supporting experiments under real-life conditions in field experiments on research field stations and lighthouse farms
- Initiating and supporting focused scientific work in controlled laboratories and field experiments

Promote faster uptake of solutions by:

- Supporting demonstration activities on e.g. lighthouse farms
- Foster collaboration between private partners (farmers, industry etc.) and investors
- Integrate governmental regulators in the co-design process to design more socio-economically sustainable solutions and overcome regulatory barriers
- Creating dialogue platforms to align agricultural innovations with policy frameworks and funding mechanisms.

We need urgent action to transform our agrifood systems for the Four Betters: better production, better nutrition, a better environment and a better life, leaving no one behind. Improving soil health through sustainable management is a game changer to achieve this goal. Soil is the foundation of our agricultural systems, the home of biodiversity, the 'green water' reservoir for our plants, and the start of our food!

**DR QU DONGYU, FAO DIRECTOR-GENERAL | 3 JUNE 2024, 12TH
PLENARY ASSEMBLY OF THE GLOBAL SOIL PARTNERSHIP**

CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (= > mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with interest in soil health, local or regional governments, scientists from a variety of fields outside soil (natural sciences, social, and behavioural sciences), the wider public

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ESS
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods, dimensions** (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup** for **ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

*adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)

LIGHTHOUSES

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, the criteria for selecting them will be based on the **mission objectives**, indicators, and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme:

- **Demonstration, dissemination, and promotion** to soil managers, the public, and the policy arena, at the landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services.
- Reaching out to the **policy arena** linking results of the Lighthouses to environmental rules and regulations. This is in line with science-based policy support and governance.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? TWO LIVING LAB TOPICS

1) Brownfield

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01: Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of **brownfields**

- **Single-stage** submission
- **Deadline:** 30 September 2025
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - should be located in at least three different Member States and/or Associated Countries

2) Biogeographical regions

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01-two-stage: Living labs to enhance soil health in **Continental, Boreal and Alpine biogeographical regions**

- **Two-stage** submission (First, applicants submit a brief outline. Selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline:** 4 September 2025 (first stage) and 18 February 2026 (second stage).
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - **Most of the living labs** (i.e., 3 out of 4, or 4 out of 5) must be located **within the chosen region**

Research and Innovation Actions:

100% funding for any actor
Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
Financial support to third parties is allowed

WANT TO EXPLORE FURTHER?

Biogeographical Regions factsheet

Both Living Lab topics on the SOILL website

FOLLOW THE SOILL PROJECT!

Check out
for updates

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space
dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts
ready to provide guidance and
answers on many topics.